

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF LULICONAZOLE TOPICAL HYDROGEL FOR FUNGAL INFECTIONS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20132895>

How to cite this Article: Pooja P.¹, Krishnananda Kamath K.¹, A. Ramakrishna Shabaraya¹, Abinash Sharma^{2*}. (2026). Design and Development of Luliconazole Topical Hydrogel for Fungal Infections. European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 13(5), 360–370.

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Article Received on 17/04/2026

Article Revised on 07/05/2026

Article Published on 10/05/2026

ABSTRACT

Luliconazole is an antifungal medicine used for the treatment of fungal infections. Luliconazole has a restrictive pharmaceutical role because of its poor aqueous solubility and skin penetration capability, which reduces the bioavailability of the drug. The present investigation was carried out to formulate and evaluate the Luliconazole nanocrystals loaded hydrogel. Nanocrystals were prepared by the modified nanoprecipitation method and were stabilized by using poloxamer 188 and PVP K-30 as stabilizers. The nanocrystals were developed by varying the concentration of surfactant and stirring speed to study the effect of particle size and PDI as dependent variables. The prepared batch was evaluated for various parameters. The prepared batch showed a particle size of 234.2nm and PDI of 0.430. Optical microscope revealed plate-like morphology of nanocrystals. Nanocrystals showed a surface charge of -24.7 mV. Results of the saturation solubility study suggested an improvement in the solubility of Luliconazole. The nanocrystal formulation was incorporated into hydrogel prepared using 1% w/w Polyvinyl alcohol and studied for Physical appearance, pH, drug content uniformity, viscosity, spreadability, *in-vitro* drug release study, kinetic studies, and stability studies. The prepared hydrogel was homogenous with 86.72% drug content and % cumulative drug release of 83.45% at the end of 8hrs. Stability studies indicated that hydrogel loaded with Luliconazole nanocrystal was stable. The findings of the study suggested that the developed formulation would be a promising delivery system with improved efficacy, controlled release, and patient compliance.

KEYWORDS: Luliconazole, Nanocrystals, Fungal Infection, Hydrogel.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, nanotechnology-based drug delivery systems have gained significant attention for overcoming the challenges associated with poor solubility and bioavailability of hydrophobic drugs. Nearly 40% of newly developed drugs exhibit poor aqueous solubility, resulting in low bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy. Conventional drug delivery systems often fail to achieve optimal absorption or localized action due to these limitations. Hence, the formulation of nanocarrier-based systems, particularly nanocrystals, has emerged as a promising approach to enhance solubility, dissolution rate, and permeation of poorly soluble drugs.^[1]

Nanocrystals are pure solid drug particles with particle sizes typically below 1 μm , stabilized by surfactants or

polymers to prevent aggregation.^[2] This approach increases the surface area-to-volume ratio and improves dissolution velocity according to the Noyes–Whitney equation, leading to higher apparent solubility. Nanocrystal technology offers several advantages such as high drug loading, enhanced bioavailability, dose proportionality, and the feasibility of administration through multiple routes including oral, intravenous, ocular, pulmonary, and dermal. It also minimizes the use of excipients, making it an industrially scalable and biocompatible drug delivery platform. However, nanocrystal formulations require stabilizers to maintain colloidal stability and are prone to physicochemical instability such as aggregation and crystal growth during processing and storage.^[3,4]

Nanocrystals are commonly produced using top-down techniques such as high-pressure homogenization and media milling, or bottom-up methods like precipitation from solvent–antisolvent systems. Combination (hybrid) techniques such as modified nanoprecipitation are often employed to achieve controlled particle size distribution and better physical stability. The modified nanoprecipitation method involves dissolving the drug in an organic solvent and introducing it into an aqueous phase containing stabilizers under homogenization or sonication. This results in rapid supersaturation, nucleation, and formation of uniform nanocrystals with improved solubility and dissolution behavior.^[5,6]

Topical drug delivery is one of the most effective and patient-compliant routes for local treatment of skin infections. It provides direct access to the target site, avoids first-pass metabolism, reduces systemic side effects, and ensures prolonged therapeutic action. However, the main limitation of topical formulations is the stratum corneum, which serves as a major barrier for drug permeation. The use of nanocrystals in topical formulations can enhance drug penetration through the skin via mechanisms such as passive diffusion, adhesiveness, diffusional corona formation, hair follicle targeting, and endocytosis. Nanocrystals adhere strongly to the skin surface, remain in close contact for an extended period, and create a supersaturated drug concentration at the application site, which enhances passive diffusion into deeper skin layers.^[7,8]

Hydrogels are three-dimensional, cross-linked polymeric networks capable of holding large amounts of water while maintaining structural integrity. They exhibit soft, elastic, and biocompatible properties that mimic biological tissues, making them ideal for topical drug delivery. Hydrogels provide a cooling effect, spread easily, and offer controlled or sustained drug release. Incorporating nanocrystals into hydrogels combines the benefits of both systems, improving the solubility, stability, and controlled release of poorly soluble drugs.^[9,10]

Fungal infections are among the most common dermatological disorders worldwide, affecting approximately 20–25% of the global population. They are caused mainly by dermatophytes, yeasts, and molds and are classified into superficial, cutaneous, and subcutaneous infections depending on the depth of fungal invasion. Conventional antifungal therapies such as creams, ointments, and oral formulations often show poor skin penetration and limited drug retention at the

site of infection, resulting in incomplete eradication and frequent recurrence. Moreover, oral antifungal therapy is associated with adverse systemic effects, drug interactions, and hepatotoxicity, emphasizing the need for safer and more effective topical alternatives.^[11,12]

Luliconazole, an imidazole derivative, is a broad-spectrum antifungal agent that acts by inhibiting cytochrome P450 14 α -demethylase, an essential enzyme for ergosterol biosynthesis in fungal cell membranes. Despite its potent antifungal activity, the drug’s clinical efficacy is restricted due to poor aqueous solubility and limited skin penetration, leading to low bioavailability. Therefore, developing a nanocrystal-based topical hydrogel system for luliconazole can significantly improve its solubility, dermal permeation, and therapeutic effectiveness while reducing the dosing frequency and minimizing side effects.^[13] The current study focuses on the design and development of luliconazole nanocrystals-loaded hydrogel to enhance solubility and skin permeability of the drug for effective treatment of fungal infections. The developed formulation aims to overcome the limitations of conventional topical dosage forms by providing enhanced penetration, prolonged drug release, improved patient compliance, and reduced recurrence of fungal infections.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Luliconazole, Polaxomer 188, methanol, PVP K-30, Polyvinylalcohol were purchased from Yarrow chemical, Mumbai, India. Propylene glycol was purchased from Loba chemical, Mumbai, India.

Preparation of Nanocrystals^[14,15]

Nanocrystal formulations were prepared by Modified nanoprecipitation method. Initially Drug was dissolved in methanol(1% w/v) and poloxamer 188 was dissolved in 50ml of water (0.03-0.17%w/v). The above organic solution of drug was added to the aqueous solution of poloxamer 188 using a syringe while continuously stirring with a mechanical stirrer. The aqueous solution was maintained at 2 °C using ice bath while stirring for immediate precipitation. Formed dispersion was stirred for an additional half an hour and probe sonicated for 30 min at 600 Watt while maintaining the dispersion at 25 °C. Nanocrystals were collected by centrifuging for 30min at 4000 rpm. Obtained nanocrystals were redispersed in 0.5 %w/v PVP K-30 for an interval of time while stirring to obtain modified nanocrystals, which were collected by centrifugation at 4000 rpm and dried at room temperature.

Table no. 01: Formulation chart of nanocrystals.

SI. No.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Luliconazole (% w/v)	1	1	1	1
2	Methanol (ml)	10	10	10	10
3	Poloxamer 188 (% w/v)	0.03	0.03	0.17	0.17
4	Distilled water (ml)	50	50	50	50
5	Stirring speed (rpm)	1600	2200	1600	2200
6	PVP K-30 (% w/v)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5

CHARACTERIZATION OF LULICONAZOLE NANOCRYSTALS^[16,17,18]

1. Surface Morphology Study

The luliconazole loaded nanocrystals were characterized using high polarising microscope for structural attributes such as uniformity of size, crystallinity and shape.

2. Particle size and zeta potential analysis

Particle size was measured using biovis particle size analyzer and zeta potential was measured using Zeta sizer (Malvern Instruments, UK) based on the dynamic light scattering principle.

3. Determination of drug content

The drug content of Luliconazole nanocrystals dried at room temperature was determined using UV-visible Spectrophotometer. 10mg of nanocrystals was dissolved in 10mL methanol in a 10mL volumetric flask followed by filtration (Whatman filter paper). The concentration of filtrate was determined spectrophotometrically at a λ_{max} of 300nm after appropriate dilution.

4. Saturation solubility study

The saturation solubility study was carried out in phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Excess of LNC was added to 10 mL of solvent and the mixtures were shaken for 24 h at 37 °C. Suspensions were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min; the supernatant was removed and thereby analyzed spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} of 300nm after appropriate dilutions for drug concentration.

5. *In vitro* dissolution study

The *in vitro* powder dissolution study of LZL and LNC was determined using USP Apparatus 2 dissolution tester. The dissolution test was carried out in 900mL of P^H 7.4 buffer with rotating speed of 50rpm and temperature maintained at 37°C ± 0.5°C. An equivalent amount of drug was introduced directly into the dissolution medium. At predetermined time interval, 5mL of sample was withdrawn and replaced with fresh medium. Samples were filtered and analyzed at observed λ_{max} of 300 nm. Three replicate dissolution tests were performed for each formulation.

Preparation of luliconazole nanocrystal loaded hydrogel^[19]

Luliconazole hydrogel was prepared by physical cross-linking method. Each ingredient (PVA, PVP-30 OR PVPK-90) will be weighed. Then these ingredients were mixed in beaker with the required amount of water. Subsequently, the beaker was sealed and heated for 25min at 65-70 °C until a clear gel was formed. To prevent the loss of water due to evaporation, the weight of the hydrogel was equalized with the initial water content and then the required amount of PG and glycerol were added.

CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOCRYSTAL LOADED HYDROGEL

1. Physical appearance^[20]

The prepared hydrogel was examined for clarity, color, homogeneity, and the presence of foreign particles.

2. pH determination^[20]

1g of gel was accurately weighed and dispersed in 100 mL of distilled water. The pH of the dispersion was measured by using digital pH meter.

3. Analysis of drug content uniformity^[21]

To ensure the homogeneity of Luliconazole in the developed LNC gel, a 0.5 g sample was taken from three different areas of the gel. Each portion of the sample was extracted in methanol (10 mL) and centrifuged (3000 rpm) for 15 min. The sample supernatant was filtered and quantified for the Luliconazole content through UV-visible spectrophotometric analysis with λ_{max} at 300nm. The % content of Luliconazole in the sample was analyzed in triplicate.

4. Determination of viscosity^[22]

The viscosity of formulated hydrogel was determined using Brookfield viscometer using Spindle no.64 at 100 rpm. Measurements were done in triplicate and the average of the readings was taken.

5. Spreadability study^[23]

To determine the spreadability of the formulated hydrogel, 0.5 g of LNC hydrogel was placed on a slide and covered with another slide on top. A weight of 50 g was placed over the top slide and was kept as such for 2 min. Post completion of the given time point of the study, the weight was lifted and the diameter of the spread gel was measured.

The following equation was used for calculating the spreadability factor:

$$Sf = W.L/T$$

Where,

Sf' = spreadability factor

L = Length moved by glass slide

'W' = weight on the slide

6. *In-vitro* diffusion study^[24,25]

The *in-vitro* drug release from gel formulation was studied across cellophane membrane using a Franz-type diffusion cell. The cellophane membrane was mounted between the donor and receptor compartments of the diffusion cell. The receiver compartment was filled with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 solution to ensure sink condition. The donor compartment of the cell was filled with 1g of the gel. The medium was agitated using a magnetic stirrer (200 rpm) at a temperature of 37 ± 0.5°C. 5 mL sample was withdrawn at an interval of 1 hour for a period of 8 hours, and each time the equal volume was replaced with drug-free receptor fluid. The aliquots were suitably diluted with receptor medium and

analyzed by UV-visible spectrophotometer at λ_{max} 300 nm.

7. Determination of drug release kinetics^[26,27]

Release kinetics of drug from the dosage form was determined by various mathematical models such as zero order, first order Koresmeyer-peppas and Higuchi model

1. Cumulative percentage drug released Vs time (zero order plots)
2. Log cumulative percentage drug remaining Vs time (first order plots)
3. Cumulative percentage drug release Vs square root of time (Higuchi plots)
4. Log cumulative percentage drug release Vs log time (koresmeyer-peppas plots)

8. Stability studies^[28,29]

The hydrogel formulation to evaluate its physical and chemical stability over time. The formulation was stored

under two different conditions as per ICH guidelines: at refrigeration temperature (4 ± 2 °C) and at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) with $60 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity for a period of 90 days. To prevent interaction between the formulation and container, the sample was stored in borosilicate glass containers. During the study period, the formulation was periodically examined for physical changes such as color, appearance, and phase separation, and was further evaluated for drug content and *in-vitro* drug release profile.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preparation of Luliconazole nanocrystal by modified nanoprecipitation method

Nanocrystals of Luliconazole were prepared by the modified nanoprecipitation method by varying the concentrations of Poloxamer 188, and the Speed of stirring at various levels. Formulated nanocrystal was shown in Figure no.01.

Figure no.1: Preparation of nanocrystals using Magnetic stirrer and sonicator.

Figure no. 02: Nanocrystal formulation.

Characterization of Luliconazole nanocrystals

1. Surface morphology study: The surface morphology of nanocrystals was studied by using the high polarizing optical microscope shown in the Fig no.3. demonstrates the surface morphology of

luliconazole nanocrystals at a magnification power of 40x. Surface morphology demonstrated plate-shaped nanocrystals with a smooth surface.

Figure no. 03: Optical microphotographs of nanocrystal formulation.

2. Particle size analysis: The Biovis particle size analyzer was used to assess the particle size of all formulations of luliconazole nanocrystals. The particle size of the prepared luliconazole nanocrystals ranged from 233.5nm to 736.4nm as shown in table no.2. The

Formulation F2 showed smaller particle size i.e, 233.5nm. The luliconazole nanocrystal with small particle size is obtained at low concentration of poloxamer 188(0.03%).

Table no. 2: Particle size analysis of Luliconazole nanocrystals formulation.

Formulation code	Particle size (nm)	PDI
F1	736.4	0.813
F2	233.5	0.416
F3	635.1	0.458
F4	506.8	0.582

Figure no. 04: Particle size and PDI of F2 formulation.

3. Determination of zeta potential

The Zeta potential of luliconazole nanocrystal was determined by Malvern zeta sizer instrument. It was found

that zeta potential of the formulation F2 was found to be -24.7mV (Figure no.5) which indicates good stability of nanocrystal formulation.

Figure no. 5: Zeta potential of nanocrystal formulation.

4. Drug content determination

Determination of the drug content of the nanocrystals was done by using methanol as a solvent. The drug content of the formulations ranged from 85.63 to 92.75% as shown

in the table no.03. F2 showed highest drug content i.e, 92.75% confirming minimal drug loss during preparation.

Table no. 3: Drug content determination of nanocrystals.

Formulation	Drug content (%w/w) (n=3)
F1	87.66 ± 0.25
F2	92.75 ± 0.30
F3	85.63 ± 0.62
F4	90.59 ± 0.23

Data expressed as a mean ± SD (n = 3)

5. Saturation solubility study

Table no.04 presents the saturation solubility data of the luliconazole nanocrystals in phosphate buffer, pH 7.4.

The solubility of luliconazole nanocrystals was significantly enhanced in phosphate buffer when compared to pure luliconazole.

Table no. 4: Saturation solubility study of Nanocrystals.

Formulations	Solubility (mg/mL)
F1	1263 ± 0.776
F2	1.854 ± 0.522
F3	1.076 ± 0.223
F4	1.642 ± 0.352

6. In vitro release: The *in vitro* dissolution study of prepared nanocrystal was carried out by using USP Apparatus 2 dissolution tester. Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was used as the dissolution medium. The *in vitro* drug release data of different formulations were shown in table no.5 and fig no.06. The cumulative percentage drug release after 6hr was found to be in the range of 60.65 to

79.62% for all the formulation and this release data of nanocrystals compared with the *in vitro* release data of pure drug which showed the %CDR 43.52% after 6hr. Therefore, drug release from the nanocrystal formulation was faster than the pure drug. F2 showed the maximum drug release of 79.62% than the other nanocrystal formulation.

Table no: 5 In vitro drug dissolution data of pure drug and nanocrystal formulations.

Time (hr)	Pure drug (% ± SD)	F1 (% ± SD)	F2 (% ± SD)	F3 (% ± SD)	F4 (% ± SD)
0	0 ± 0.00	0 ± 0.00	0 ± 0.00	0 ± 0.00	0 ± 0.00
1	10.9 ± 0.15	11.29 ± 0.78	17.12 ± 0.34	15.26 ± 0.14	16.11 ± 0.23
2	16.05 ± 0.46	18.6 ± 0.57	24.34 ± 0.87	21.26 ± 0.42	23.21 ± 0.58
3	20.73 ± 0.20	23.39 ± 0.45	45.96 ± 0.12	35.86 ± 0.67	42.89 ± 0.22
4	29.42 ± 0.14	32.35 ± 0.28	57.97 ± 0.56	47.67 ± 0.12	54.32 ± 0.12
5	34.73 ± 0.74	43.11 ± 0.13	69.89 ± 0.43	53.56 ± 0.15	64.23 ± 0.87
6	43.52 ± 0.24	60.65 ± 0.60	79.62 ± 0.12	65.87 ± 0.32	74.23 ± 0.73

Fig no: 6 In vitro drug release studies of pure drug and nanocrystals (F1-F4).

Characterization of luliconazole nanocrystal loaded hydrogel

Based on the particle size, saturation solubility and *in vitro*

release studies, F2 was found to show the better result which was incorporated into hydrogel and subjected for further studies as shown in the table no.06.

1. Physical appearance

Table no. 6: Physical appearance of luliconazole nanocrystal loaded hydrogel.

Formulation	Color	Clarity	Homogeneity	Foreign particles
Luliconazole nanocrystal-loaded hydrogel	Off-white	Clear	Good	Absent

Figure no. 7: Luliconazole nanocrystal-loaded hydrogel

The prepared hydrogel was off-white in color. The clarity of the hydrogel was determined by visual inspection under black and white background and it was graded as clear.

The prepared hydrogel was evaluated for physical appearance. The formulation was homogenous without any gritty particles or aggregates.

2. Determination of pH, drug content uniformity, viscosity, and spreadability

Table no. 7: pH, drug content uniformity, viscosity and spreadability of the luliconazole nanocrystal loaded hydrogel (n =3).

Formulation	pH (\pm SD)	% Drug Content (\pm SD)	Viscosity (cps \pm SD)	Spreadability Factor (Sf)
Luliconazole nanocrystal-loaded hydrogel	5.81 \pm 0.32	86.72 \pm 2.41%	2071.67 \pm 6.06	10.53 \pm 0.46

a. Determination of pH

The pH of the hydrogel containing luliconazole nanocrystals was found to be 5.81 \pm 0.032 (Table no.7) which is related to the pH of the skin; hence it causes no irritation. Thus, the hydrogel was found to be compatible with the skin pH.

b. Analysis of drug content uniformity

Content uniformity between three different regions was found to be quite similar with a content uniformity of 86.72 \pm 2.41%, The results of the drug content uniformity study illustrated the suitability of the prepared hydrogel loaded with luliconazole nanocrystal for pharmacological action.

c. Determination of viscosity

The viscosity property of the formulated hydrogel containing luliconazole-loaded nanocrystals was studied

using Brookfield viscometer. The viscosity was measured at 100 rpm using a spindle number 64. The viscosity of the prepared gel was found to be 2071.67 \pm 6.06 cps (table no. 7).

d. Determination of spreadability

The spreadability of the prepared gel containing luliconazole nanocrystals was determined and its spreadability factor was found to be 10.53 \pm 0.46 (Table no.7). This showed that gel has a good spreadability which ensures ease of application. A better spreadability ensures that the gel will be spread more intimately with the skin, increasing the contact area for a small amount of the formulated gel and thereby delivery of a larger amount of the drug owing to the larger surface area for drug transposition through the skin layers.

1. In-vitro drug release study

Table no. 8: In-vitro.

Time (hr)	% Cumulative Drug Release (\pm SD)
0	0 \pm 0.00
1	13.27 \pm 0.20
2	24.63 \pm 0.45

3	35.10 ± 0.78
4	46.35 ± 0.45
5	54.14 ± 0.52
6	67.37 ± 0.66
7	75.50 ± 0.70
8	83.45 ± 0.58

Drug release of a study of hydrogel containing luliconazole nanocrystals.

Data expressed as a mean ± SD (n = 3)

Figure no. 08 : In-vitro drug release profile of luliconazole nanocrystal loaded hydrogel.

The *in-vitro* drug releases study for the hydrogel loaded with the luliconazole nanocrystals was carried out using the Franz diffusion cell which showed a cumulative %

drug release of 83.45% at the end of 8 hours. *In-vitro* release pattern of the formulation is demonstrated in Figure no.08.

2. Kinetic study

Table no. 09: Kinetic release study of hydrogel containing LNC.

Time (hr)	Log Time	√Time	% Cumulative Drug Release	Log % Drug Release	% Drug Retained	Log % Drug Retained
0	0	0	0	0	100	2
1	0	1	13.27	1.122	86.73	1.938
2	0.301	1.414	24.63	1.391	75.37	1.877
3	0.477	1.732	35.10	1.545	64.90	1.812
4	0.602	2.000	46.35	1.666	53.65	1.729
5	0.698	2.236	54.14	1.733	45.86	1.661
6	0.778	2.449	67.37	1.828	32.63	1.513
7	0.845	2.645	75.50	1.877	24.50	1.389
8	0.903	2.828	83.45	1.921	16.55	1.218

Zero order kinetic releases

Figure no. 9: Plot of % CDR Vs Time (Zero order kinetics).

Figure no. 10: Plot of Log % of drug retained Vs Time (First order kinetics).

First order kinetic release

Figure no.11: Plot of %CDR Vs SQRT.

Higuchi model

In order to study the exact mechanism of drug release from hydrogel loaded with the luliconazole nanocrystals drug release data were fitted into various mathematical models such as Zero order, First order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer- Peppas models. The data were processed for regression analysis using MS-EXCEL statistical function. The release constants were calculated from the slope of appropriate plots, and the regression coefficient

(R^2) was determined. It was found that *in-vitro* drug release of nanocrystal-loaded hydrogel was best explained by the Korsmeyer-Peppas model as the plot shows the highest linearity (Figure no. 12). Regression coefficient (R^2) was found to be 0.9992 (Table no.10) with an 'n' value of 0.8908 which showed that formulated hydrogel followed case II transport mechanism indicating zero order release of the drug.

Kosmeyers peppas model

Figure no. 12 Plot of LOG TIME Vs LOG %CDR.

Table no. 10: Kinetic release study of luliconazole nanocrystal loaded hydrogel formulation.

Formulation	Zero Order Model (R ²)	First Order Model (R ²)	Higuchi Model (R ²)	Korsmeyer–Peppas Model (R ²)	n Value
Luliconazole nanocrystal-loaded hydrogel	0.9961	0.9618	0.9392	0.9992	0.8908

Stability studies

Table no: 13 Stability study.

Evaluation Parameter (25 ± 2°C / 60 ± 5% RH)	0 Days	30 Days	60 Days	90 Days
Color	Off-white	Off-white	Off-white	Off-white
Drug content (% w/w ± SD)	86.72 ± 2.41	86.69 ± 0.15	86.65 ± 0.21	86.10 ± 0.32
In-vitro drug release (%CDR after 8 h ± SD)	83.45 ± 0.58	83.42 ± 0.26	83.38 ± 0.44	82.25 ± 0.75

Parameter (Storage condition: 40 ± 2°C)	0 Days	30 Days	60 Days	90 Days
Color	Off-white	Off-white	Off-white	Off-white
Drug content (% w/w ± SD)	86.72 ± 2.41	86.54 ± 2.54	86.15 ± 1.99	85.03 ± 1.45
In-vitro drug release (%CDR after 8 h ± SD)	83.45 ± 0.58	83.21 ± 0.19	83.16 ± 0.11	80.25 ± 0.05

The stability study was carried out for luliconazole nanocrystals loaded hydrogel at temperature conditions i.e., 25 ± 2 °C with 60 ± 5% RH and 4 ± 2 °C as per ICH guidelines. It was confirmed from the stability studies that the hydrogel containing luliconazole nanocrystals remained stable at for a period of 90 days. It was found that there were no considerable changes in pH, viscosity, drug content, and *in-vitro* drug release rate before and after 90 days of stability study as shown in Table no.13.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, luliconazole nanocrystals were successfully prepared by a modified nanoprecipitation method. The results obtained from this study revealed that prepared luliconazole nanocrystals loaded hydrogel has a great potential to improve the topical delivery of luliconazole with great patient compliance as compared with conventional formulations.

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